

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT SIZING ON FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYPHTHALAMIDE

V. Radlmaier¹, A. Erber², P.-V. Brudzinski², H. Koerber¹ and K. Drechsler¹

¹Institute for Carbon Composites, Technische Universitaet Muenchen
Boltzmannstrasse 15, D-85478 Garching, Germany

Email: radlmaier@lcc.mw.tum.de, Web page: <http://www.lcc.mw.tum.de/>

²SGL Carbon GmbH

Werner-von-Siemens-Straße 18, D-86405 Meitingen, Germany

Web page: <http://www.sglgroup.com/>

Keywords: Thermoplastic composites, Carbon fiber sizing, Mode I fracture toughness, Flexural strength

ABSTRACT

The advantages of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) can be fully exploited only when a strong interface of the matrix to the reinforcing carbon fibers is established. Since commonly available sizing materials for carbon fiber reinforced thermosets cannot withstand high temperatures during processing of thermoplastics, new sizing materials are required to avoid thermal degradation. In addition, sizing materials for CFRTP need suitable chemical groups reacting with thermoplastic matrix materials to form a strong fiber-matrix interface. In this study the effects of epoxy- and polyamide-based sizing materials on the mode I fracture toughness and the transverse flexural properties of carbon fiber reinforced polyphthalamide (PPA) were investigated. The fracture toughness test results as well as micrographs of the fractured surfaces taken by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) indicated an excellent adhesion to the matrix when the polyamide-based sizing material was employed. However, the results from the transverse flexural test show lower strength values for PPA specimen with the polyamide-compatible sizing material. This might be attributed to differences in the spreading behavior of the variously sized carbon fibers during composite production.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lately, there is an increasing interest for continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites due to several advantages such as short forming and consolidation times, unlimited shelf-life, recyclability and high fracture toughness. However, the benefits of a thermoplastic resin system can only be utilized in a composite if a strong link between matrix and fibers is established. Using thermoplastics with high fracture toughness leads only to increased delamination fracture toughness of the composite when sufficient bonding between fibers and matrix is achieved [1].

When carbon fibers are produced, they are typically surface-treated to enhance the surface roughness and oxygen amount leading to an increased reactivity of the fiber surface [2]. Often, another coating, a sizing or surface finish, is applied to the carbon fibers after surface treatment to protect the fibers from damages during handling. In addition, the sizing is employed to establish chemical bonding to both fiber and matrix. In order to obtain optimum composite properties, sizing materials are modified such that they match with the matrix material to enhance the compatibility between fibers and matrix. [3]

Due to the large share of carbon fiber reinforced epoxies in composite applications, the available carbon fibers are however predominantly compatible to epoxy matrix systems. Typical sizing materials matching with epoxy resins can consist of resin components without cross-linking agent or partially cross-linked polymers. These sizing materials are designed to cross-link with the host matrix during the composite production in order to build up a strong chemical bond between fiber and matrix [4]. Besides the lack of chemical compatibility of epoxy-based sizing materials to

thermoplastics, epoxy groups start to decompose at 250°C which represents the lower processing bound for most thermoplastics.

To avoid the issue of chemical incompatibility only surface-treated carbon fibers without surface finish were used in a previous study [5] to improve the adhesion of carbon fibers to thermoplastics. However, the authors found an increasing amount of oxygen and enhanced surface roughness to be insufficient to form a good adhesion of fibers to matrix since strong covalent bonds cannot be established. Hence, new sizing materials are required to chemically interact with the thermoplastic matrix and to withstand higher temperatures during thermoplastic composite production.

Considering the production of components made from thermoplastic composites, often intermediate materials are used shifting the time-consuming step of impregnating carbon fibers with high-viscous thermoplastics prior to actual part manufacture. During the production of intermediate materials such as unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced tapes (UD tapes) the impregnation is also influenced by the wetting ability of the matrix. Here, the sizing composition can help to reduce the contact angle while increasing the surface energy of the fiber to improve the wetting performance of the matrix [6] enabling faster micro-impregnation.

It has been shown that sizing of carbon fibers can affect the level of adhesion to the host matrix in multiple ways. Testing of selected mechanical properties directly on the composite level reveals the effective impact of the sizing on the adhesion to the matrix material. In this study two different sizing materials were employed to evaluate their effects on the mode I fracture toughness and transverse flexural properties of UD tapes with polyphthalamide (PPA) matrix.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The differently sized carbon fibers used in this study were namely SIGRAFIL C T50 - 4.0/240 - E100 (CF-EPY) and SIGRAFIL C T50 - 4.0/240 - T140 (CF-TP) made by SGL Group. Both carbon fiber types underwent the same processing steps beginning from precursor spinning to carbonization and finally to surface treatment via anodization. The only difference lies in the application of different sizing materials after surface treatment. CF-EPY was sized with an epoxy-compatible suspension and CF-TP was coated with a sizing mainly containing polyamides compatible to various polyamides. Both fiber types are compared in Table 1 regarding type and amount of sizing agents along with general properties.

Carbon fiber type	Number of filaments [k]	Sizing type	Filament diameter [μm]	Tensile modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [GPa]
SIGRAFIL C T50-4.0/240-E100 (CF-EPY)	50	epoxy-based	6.92	240	4.00
SIGRAFIL C T50-4.0/240-T140 (CF-TP)		polyamide-based			

Table 1: Comparison of differently sized carbon fibers used in this study.

The thermoplastic matrix material used for the production of UD tapes as intermediate materials for the manufacture of testing laminates was a semi-crystalline polyphthalamide supplied by Evonik (Vestamid HT plus C2000). Polyphthalamides are partially aromatic polyamides which comprise aliphatic diamine and terephthalic monomers. By incorporating terephthalic acid into aliphatic diamine the heat resistance can be increased significantly compared to aliphatic polyamides such as Polyamide 6 (PA 6) or Polyamide 66 (PA 66). Thus, polyphthalamides can fill the cost-performance gap between engineering thermoplastics such as PA 6, polyester (PET), polyacetals (POM) and high performance thermoplastics such as polyphenylene sulfide (PPS), liquid crystal polymers (LCP) or polyetherimide (PEI) [7]. In comparison to PA 6, PPA shows a higher thermal stability and less susceptibility to water absorption. The used polyphthalamide type is based on

PA 10T (1,10 diaminodecan and terephthalic acid). The constitutional formula of the repeating units is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of semi-aromatic polyamide (PA 10T).

The relevant thermal and mechanical properties of the PPA type used in this study are presented in Table 2.

	Glass transition temperature [°C]	Melting temperature [°C]	Tensile modulus [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]
Vestamid HT plus C 2000	123	265	2100	62

Table 2: Material properties of the employed thermoplastic matrix material PA 10T [8].

The glass transition temperature and the melting temperature given in Table 2 represent the mean of four CF-EPY/PPA specimen evaluated by the Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) according to DIN EN ISO 11357 [9, 10] after the second heating in order to eliminate effects due to thermal history.

2.2. Composite manufacture

For the production of the test panels spread carbon fibers with EPY and TP sizing were pre-impregnated with PPA powder (powder-prepregs) from both sides. Before the differently sized carbon fibers were brought together with the matrix material, nine carbon fiber roving were spread simultaneously to a width of approximately 200 mm. First effects of the different sizing materials were observed after spreading. By using carbon fibers with epoxy-based sizing, the roving were spread to a width of 205 mm. When the TP carbon fibers were spread, a width of 180 mm was obtained. The reduction in width resulted in an increase in thickness of CF-TP/PPA powder-prepregs compared to CF-EPY/PPA powder-prepregs.

After manufacturing, the powder-prepregs were cut to a length of 300 to 390 mm and the single plies were stacked to obtain test plates. Test panels determined for testing transverse flexural properties according to DIN EN ISO 14125 [11] require a nominal thickness of 2 mm. For testing the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties, test panels with a nominal thickness of 3 mm are required according to ASTM D 5528 [12]. Different amounts of prepregs plies were necessary to produce the nominal thickness of the test panels due to the different prepreg widths obtained after spreading. The spread powder-prepreg width together with the required amount of plies to be stacked for generating the nominal thickness of the test panels are presented in Table 3.

Material Combination	Spread powder-prepreg width [mm]	Lay-up Transverse Flexural Test	Lay-up Mode I Interlaminar Fracture toughness
CF-EPY/PPA	205	[0] ₁₂	[0] ₂₂
CF-TP/PPA	180	[0] ₁₁	[0] ₂₀

Table 3: Powder-prepreg width after spreading of CF-EPY and CF-TP along with the resulting difference in number of plies required for test panels.

A polyimide foil with a thickness of 25 µm was deposited at the midplane of the laminate during lay-up of the fracture toughness specimen to generate an initial delamination length. Before the

polyimide foil strips were positioned between the powder-prepreg plies they were coated with high-temperature resistant release agent. All powder-prepreg stacks were then dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C for at least 4 hours. After drying, each stack was put in a press already heated to 300°C. Before pressure was applied, the temperature was held constant until uniform heating of the prepreg stacks was achieved. Then, pressure of 10 bar was applied. After holding pressure and temperature constant for 30 minutes each laminate was cooled to 80°C with a cooling rate of 20°C/min.

After production of the test panels micrographs at three different locations of each plate were prepared in order to inspect the quality of the produced laminates. Details of the test panels that are representative of the entire laminate are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Micrographs of test panels before testing: a) and b) CF-EPY/PPA; c) and d) CF-TP/PPA.

The prepared micrographs in Figure 2 confirm the observations made after spreading of the differently sized carbon fibers. Thinner plies can be obtained for the carbon fibers with epoxy-based sizing, compared to carbon fibers with polyamide-compatible sizing. In case of CF-EPY, the single plies of the test panels can be identified without difficulty (see Figure 2a). The test panels made from CF-TP/PPA show a less regular ply lay-up with merging plies (see Figure 2b). However, this effect is reduced when thicker test panels are produced for interlaminar fracture toughness tests (see Figure 2d).

2.3 Test setup and procedures

Transverse flexural tests according to DIN EN ISO 14125 B and mode I fracture toughness tests in accordance to the double-cantilever beam (DCB) test method (ASTM D 5528) were chosen to determine the effect of the EPY and TP sizing with PPA matrix on the fiber-matrix interaction. All test samples were cut from the pressed laminates to the required dimensions by using a water-cooled circular diamond saw.

The DCB specimen were coated with white water-based fluid and marked beginning from the insert according to [12] to visualize the crack propagation during testing. For determination of the transverse flexural properties the four-point bend test setup was chosen due to the advantage of a constant bending moment without introduction of shear. After cutting, all test specimen were dried in a vacuum oven at 110°C for at least 60 hours to ensure complete water removal.

The transverse flexural test specimen with a span-to-depth ratio of 40 were conducted with a crosshead speed of 2.15 mm/min (according to section 9.3 (2) in [11]) in a Hegewald and Peschke

universal testing machine at room temperature. The support span was nominally 45 mm, the load span 15 mm. The deflection of the specimen was detected with a video extensometer with telecentric lenses to determine the transverse flexural modulus. After testing of five specimen the evaluation of the transverse flexural test specimen (Figure 3a) was carried out according to DIN EN ISO 14125 B.

For testing mode I fracture toughness all five specimen were positioned in a test fixture according to the Side Clamped Beam (SCB) hinge system developed by Renart et al. [13] (Figure 3b). Using this fixture the time-consuming bonding of loading blocks to the test specimen can be avoided. In addition, testing of SCB specimen at elevated temperatures can be conducted without difficulty [13].

Figure 3: a) Four-point bend testing showing marks to detect the specimens' deflection by a video extensometer, b) testing mode I interlaminar fracture toughness by using the SCB test fixture.

The initial loading to generate a delamination growth of 3 to 5 mm as well as the reloading of each specimen until fracture was conducted with a crosshead speed of 3.00 mm/min. Both loading cycles were recorded with a camera with two frames per second. By connecting the universal testing machine to the camera software, force and displacement values corresponding to the recorded pictures were used for calculating interlaminar fracture toughness of the CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA test specimen. The opening mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} and the delamination resistance curve (R curve) were calculated by visual observation and by using the Modified Compliance Calibration (MCC) method.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Transverse flexural properties

The load-displacement curves for CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA test specimen during four-point bend testing are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Load-displacement curves recorded during four-point bend testing of a) CF-EPY/PPA and b) CF-TP/PPA specimen.

Comparing the load-displacement curves in Figure 4, CF-EPY/PPA specimen withstand to higher loads than CF-TP/PPA specimen. Within the CF-EPY/PPA test series specimen PPA_EPY_04 exhibits a decrease of load to a residual force level. This behavior can be observed for CF-TP/PPA specimen even to a greater extent. Here, three specimen did not show a failure at once but a drop in force to a residual level. For specimen without failure after reaching the maximum force, the test was stopped manually after a displacement of 2 mm since the test specimen start to deform plastically.

Relating the force and the support span length to the correspondent cross sectional area of each specimen yields the flexural stress (according to section 10.2.1 (8) in [11]). For each specimen of both test series the flexural stress was plotted against the midspan deflection recorded by a video extensometer. The stress-deflection curves obtained for all tested CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA specimen are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Stress-deflection curves of a) CF-EPY/PPA and b) CF-TP/PPA specimen.

Plotting transverse flexural stress against midspan deflection reveals comparable values for deflection for the two test series with lower stress values for CF-TP/PPA specimen with the polyamide-based sizing.

3.2 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness

The load-displacement curves for CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA test specimen during mode I interlaminar fracture toughness testing after initial loading are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Load-displacement curves for PPA test specimen with a) epoxy-based carbon fiber sizing and with b) polyamide-based sizing during DCB test after crack initiation.

By comparing the force level of both test series in Figure 6 an increase in mean maximum force by 17 % is noticed for PPA specimen with polyamide-based carbon fiber sizing. In addition, a larger displacement can be observed for the CF-TP/PPA specimen.

The R curves including visually observed initiation values for opening mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} and propagation values of the PPA specimen with EPY and TP sizing are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The delamination resistance curve with opening mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} for a) CF-EPY/PPA specimen and b) CF-TP/PPA specimen.

The R curves of the CF-EPY/PPA specimen in Figure 7 on the left show low scatter in the test results and the values of opening mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} are found to be lower compared to CF-TP/PPA. After crack initiation, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_I of CF-TP/PPA specimen further increase considerably, compared to CF-EPY/PPA specimen.

3.3 Fracture analysis

In order to understand the failure modes of the tested specimen the fractured surface of tested specimen was analyzed under a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Figure 8 shows the fractured surface of representative CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA specimen after transverse flexural testing.

In comparison to CF-EPY/PP specimen, the fracture surface of CF-TP/PPA specimen show a pattern of several broken fiber bundles when 100-times magnified. Increasing the magnification level to 1,500-times, the fractured surface of CF-EPY/PPA specimen after transverse flexural testing reveals comparatively clean fibers with low amount of residual matrix on the fiber surfaces. On the contrary, the carbon fibers with polyamide-based sizing are almost completely coated with matrix material.

The fractured surface of specimen after testing mode I interlaminar fracture toughness testing was investigated, too. SEM micrographs of representative specimen of both test series CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA are presented in Figure 9. When the fractured surfaces are 500-times magnified, the carbon fibers of CF-EPY/PPA specimen appear clean with less amount of residual matrix material on fiber surfaces compared to CF-TP/PPA specimen. At 2,500-times magnification, it can be seen that the matrix cleanly strips off from fibers with epoxy-compatible sizing. The carbon fibers of CF-TP/PPA specimen are nearly completely covered with PPA matrix.

Figure 8: SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces after transverse flexural testing: a) and b) CF-EPY/PPA; c) and d) CF-TP/PPA; (a) and c) 100-times magnified; b) and d) 1,500-times magnified).

Figure 9: SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces after DCB testing: a) and b) CF-EPY/PPA; c) and d) CF-TP/PPA; (a) and c) 500-times magnified; b) and d) 2,500-times magnified).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results gained from testing specimen with carbon fibers comprising of an epoxy-compatible and polyamide-based sizing, embedded in a PPA matrix, are contrary. Testing the transverse flexural strength in a four-point bend test and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, similar tendencies of the test results were expected. While transverse flexural strength decreased by 19 % when the polyamide-based sizing was applied, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness increased by 44 % in comparison to PPA specimen with epoxy-sizing. Figure 10 presents the different tendencies in test results of CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA specimen obtained during four-point-bend and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness testing.

Figure 10: Comparison of the mean test results gained during testing transverse flexural and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties of CF-EPY/PPA and CF-TP/PPA specimen.

Considering the present test results, an explanation for the divergent outcome might be found in the composite manufacturing. Both carbon fibers underwent the same spreading process with previous process parameter optimization. CF-EPY/PPA powder-prepregs could be more spread than CF-TP/PPA powder-prepregs, resulting in a difference of 14 % in prepreg width after spreading. In addition, the polyamide-sized carbon fibers were not as homogeneously spread as CF-EPY showing small disconnected gaps. Micrographs of the test panels prepared before testing (section 2.2) show partially little spread roving and fiber agglomerations in case of CF-TP/PPA specimen. Areas with locally high fiber volume content, resulting from fiber agglomerations discovered in the micrographs, are attributed to inhomogeneous spreading of the CF-TP/PPA powder-prepregs. It is assumed that these areas led to premature failure of the specimen during four-point bend testing. This assumption seems to be confirmed by observations made during the fracture analysis using SEM. The fractured surface of CF-TP/PPA specimen after transverse tensile testing show several broken fiber agglomerations which were also noticed in the micrographs.

Another reason for the decrease in transverse flexural strength of CF-TP/PPA specimen might be a poor adhesion of the fibers to the matrix. However, indications for a weak link between fibers and matrix were not found during fracture analysis. By increasing the magnification level, a good adhesion of PPA matrix to carbon fibers with polyamide-based sizing is argued from the great extent of residual matrix material on fiber surfaces (Figure 9d). Thus, a poor adhesion of carbon fiber with polyamide-based sizing to PPA is eliminated to be the reason for premature failure during transverse flexural testing.

The increased mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of CF-TP/PPA specimen compared to CF-EPY/PPA leads to the assumption that a chemical bonding of the PPA matrix to the carbon fibers with polyamide-based sizing could be set up. Obviously, the epoxy groups of the EPY sizing cannot form strong chemical bonds such as covalent bonding to polyamide matrix systems. However, secondary intermolecular forces such as van der Waals forces can develop. The SEM micrographs of CF-EPY/PPA specimen reveal only little amount of residual matrix on the carbon fibers. This low interaction between fibers and matrix can be attributed to developed van der Waals forces but is a sign of poor adhesion of EPY carbon fibers to PPA matrix. In contrast, carbon fibers with polyamide-based sizing are nearly completely covered with PPA matrix indicating a strong link between TP fibers and PPA matrix as also found in the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test results.

The increasing propagation values G_I of CF-TP/PPA specimen could have been provoked by fiber bridging that was observed for this test series to a greater extent.

Altogether, the polyamide-based sizing reveals a good chemical compatibility to the PPA matrix as seen in the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test results and the analysis of the fracture surface via SEM. However, more efforts regarding an improved spreading process have to be made to obtain equal quality composite laminates for both sizing materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the TUM Institute of Medical and Polymer Engineering for the support in conducting SEM measurements.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Rikards, F.-G. Buchholz, A. K. Bledzki, G. Wacker, and A. Korjakin, Mode I, mode II, and mixed-mode I/II interlaminar fracture toughness of GFRP influenced by fiber surface treatment, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, **32** (5), 1996, pp. 439–462.
- [2] D. Upadhyaya and P. Tsakirooulos, Evaluation of the effect of sizing levels on transverse flexural and shear strengths of carbon/epoxy composites, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **54** (1-4), 1995, pp. 17–20.
- [3] G. Wacker, A. K. Bledzki, and A. Chate, Effect of interphase on the transverse Young's modulus of glass/epoxy composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **29** (5-6), 1998, pp. 619–626.
- [4] L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich, M. F. Koenig, and P. F. Lloyd, Adhesion of Graphite Fibers to Epoxy Matrices: II. The Effect of Fiber Finish, *The Journal of Adhesion*, **16**, 1983, pp. 133–152.
- [5] L. T. Drzal and V. K. Raghavendran, Adhesion of Thermoplastic Matrices to Carbon Fibers: Effect of Polymer Molecular Weight and Fiber Surface Chemistry, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **16** (1), 2003, pp. 21–30.
- [6] H. Yuan, S. Zhang, and C. Lu, Surface modification of carbon fibers by a polyether sulfone emulsion sizing for increased interfacial adhesion with polyether sulfone, *Applied Surface Science*, **317**, 2014, pp. 737–744.
- [7] H. P. Schmeer, Polyphthalamid: Technischer Kunststoff - Hochleistungspolymer - Automobilindustrie, *Kautschuk, Gummi, Kunststoffe*, **46** (10), 1993, pp. 799–804.
- [8] Evonik Industries AG, VESTAMID HTplus C2000, C2505: The new high-temperature polyamide for composites, 2012, Retrieved from <http://www.vestamid.de/sites/dc/Downloadcenter/Evonik/Product/VESTAMID/en/brochures/flyer-vestamid-htplus-composites.pdf>.
- [9] DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., Kunststoffe – Dynamische Differenz-Thermoanalyse (DSC) – Teil 3: Bestimmung der Schmelz- und Kristallisationstemperatur und der Schmelz- und Kristallisationsenthalpie (ISO 11357-3:2011), Beuth Verlag, Berlin, 2013.
- [10] DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., Kunststoffe – Dynamische Differenz-Thermoanalyse (DSC) - Teil 2: Bestimmung der Glasübergangstemperatur und der Glasübergangsstufenhöhe (ISO 11357-2:2013), Beuth Verlag, Berlin, 2014.
- [11] DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., Faserverstärkte Kunststoffe – Bestimmung der Biegeeigenschaften (EN ISO 14125-1:2011), Beuth Verlag, Berlin, 2011.
- [12] ASTM Standard D 5528-01, Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, 2001.
- [13] J. Renart, N. Blanco, E. Pajares, J. Costa, S. Lazcano, and G. Santacruz, Side Clamped Beam (SCB) hinge system for delamination tests in beam-type composite specimens, *Composites Science and Technology*, **71** (8), 2011, pp. 1023–1029.